

DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: ASSESSING THEIR UTILIZATION AND PERCEIVED EFFECT ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the utilization of digital platforms in English Language Teaching and their perceived effects on English language acquisition among elementary learners at Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School, City of Ilagan, Isabela. Specifically, it examined the profiles of teacher- and learner-respondents, the digital platforms used in English instruction, teachers' perceptions of platform utilization, learners' perceptions of their effects on language acquisition, the relationship between respondents' profiles and their perceptions, and the challenges encountered in using digital tools. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Respondents included 10 teachers and 106 Grade 3 to Grade 6 learners who had exposure to digital platforms in English instruction. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, and Chi-square test of independence. Findings revealed that Messenger and YouTube were the most frequently utilized platforms, while other tools such as Google Classroom, Kahoot, Quizizz, Duolingo, Zoom, and Canva were generally underutilized. Teacher-respondents strongly agreed that digital platforms were usable, effective, and beneficial in enhancing English instruction. Learner-respondents also strongly agreed that digital platforms improved engagement, confidence, motivation, comprehension, and overall English language development. Results further showed no significant relationship between respondents' profiles and their perceptions of digital platform utilization and effects. However, challenges such as poor internet connectivity, limited access to devices, inadequate training, technical issues, digital distractions, and cost-related barriers were identified. The study concludes that digital platforms positively support English language

teaching and acquisition, provided that infrastructure, training, and access-related concerns are addressed

Keywords: *Digital Platforms, English Language Teaching, English Language Acquisition, Learner Engagement, Elementary Learners*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of technology has significantly transformed education, particularly in English Language Teaching (ELT), where digital platforms have become essential tools for learning. The global pandemic further accelerated the integration of these tools, as educators were compelled to adapt to alternative methods to sustain teaching and learning in the absence of face-to-face classes. This shift highlighted both the potential and the challenges of using digital platforms in facilitating language acquisition.

Despite widespread use, questions remain regarding the effectiveness of digital platforms in enhancing students' English language skills, especially at the elementary level. Digital tools have the capacity to improve learners' motivation and attitudes by supporting differentiated instruction based on their language proficiency and individual characteristics, while also providing immediate feedback and fostering active interaction. However, the extent to which these benefits are realized in actual classroom contexts continues to require careful examination (Handayani, 2024; Schindler et al., 2017; Yolanda et al., 2025).

The researcher has observed the increasing reliance on digital platforms in teaching, particularly during and after the pandemic. These observations have led to a growing interest in understanding how such tools influence learners' engagement and language development. The integration of technology in education is no longer optional but a necessity, as it has become a primary medium for instruction during periods when traditional classroom settings were not possible (Berková et al., 2024; UNESCO, 2023).

In Southeast Asia, initiatives such as those promoted by the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization emphasize digital literacy as a key component of educational development. In the Philippines, where internet and social media usage is notably high, the importance of digital tools in education is recognized in policies such as Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, which supports the strengthening of the basic education curriculum and the improvement of teaching and learning outcomes. Guided by these realities and observations, this study is conducted to better understand the role and effectiveness of digital platforms in English language teaching among elementary learners (Republic Act No. 10533, 2013; Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization, 2023; UNESCO, 2023).

At the local level, Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School represents a microcosm of the challenges and opportunities posed by digital platforms in education. Teachers in Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School increasingly rely on tools such as Google

Classroom, Messenger, and Canva to supplement traditional teaching methods. However, the effectiveness of these platforms in improving English language skills remains underexplored. Recent school reports indicate that while 85% of learners have access to digital devices, only 60% were reported to feel confident in using these platforms for academic purposes. Furthermore, according to the data recorded by Philippine Statistics in 2025³, 18.9 million Filipino learners who graduated from junior and senior high school in 2024 are considered functionally illiterate; they can read but have difficulty in understanding.

While its benefits are evident, the use of digital platforms in ELT faces several challenges. Primarily, the digital divide limits access to technology, particularly in rural and underprivileged areas, creating disparities in learning opportunities. Additionally, inadequate digital literacy among teachers and learners can hinder effective platform utilization. Technical issues such as unstable internet connectivity and lack of proper training further complicate the seamless integration of digital tools. Moreover, over-reliance on digital platforms may reduce face-to-face interactions, potentially affect the development of speaking and listening skills in language learning.

This study is guided by the mandates of the Department of Education (2022) and highlights the Digital Rise Program as a key player in addressing challenges in education quality, which aims to enhance 21st-century skills, including digital literacy and language proficiency. By assessing the utilization of digital platforms in Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School and their impact on learners' English language acquisition, this research aimed to provide empirical evidence that informs educators, policymakers, and stakeholders about the potential and challenges of digital integration in ELT. Ultimately, this study sought to bridge gaps between policy, practice, and pedagogy, ensuring that technology serves as a catalyst for meaningful learning experiences in the English language classroom.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the utilization of digital platforms in English Language Teaching (ELT) and their perceived effects on learners' English language acquisition at Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School. It was intended to identify the role of digital platforms in developing learners' English proficiency addressing gaps and challenges to improve teaching practices.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondent in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Plantilla Position
 - d. Highest Educational Attainment
 - e. Grade Level Taught
2. What is the profile of the learner-respondent in terms of:

- a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Grade level
3. What digital platforms are utilized by teachers in English Language Teaching?
4. How do the teacher-respondent perceive the utilization of digital platforms in English Language Teaching. In terms of:
 - a. Usability and Integration
 - b. Perceived Effectiveness
 - c. Overall Perception
5. Is there significant relationship between the teacher-respondents' profile and their perception on the utilization of digital platforms on English Language Teaching?
6. How do the learner-respondents' perceive the effects of digital platforms in English Language Acquisition?
 - a. Learner Engagement
 - b. Impact
 - c. Overall Perceived Effect
7. Is there significant relationship between the learner-respondents profile and their perception on the effect of digital platforms on English Language Acquisition?
8. What are the challenges encountered by the teachers and learners in the utilization of digital platforms?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational method of research was utilized in this study to examine the utilization of digital platforms in English Language Teaching (ELT) and their effects on learners' English acquisition. Descriptive correlational research design is used to uncover relationships between variables without manipulating them. In this method, researchers can observe and analyze how two or more characteristics interact in their natural settings. Instead of intervening, you simply listen and observe—a principle at the heart of customer-centric practices (Barooah, 2026). This method allowed the researcher to describe the current practices, perceptions, and profiles of teachers and learners, while also analyzing relationships between variables, such as teacher and learner characteristics and their perceptions of digital platform use. It is particularly appropriate because it involves observing existing conditions without manipulating variables, providing both a clear view of current practices and insights into potential associations.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School located at Cabannungan 2nd City of Ilagan, Isabela. The school is under the Northwest District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. Consisting of 13 teaching personnel and 3 non-teaching personnel.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study consisted of 106 Grade 3-6 elementary learners of Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School. The selected learner respondents chosen were selected from those with the frequent exposure to digital platforms in English language instruction. The selection process ensured that the data gathered are relevant and reflective of the study's focus on digital platform utilization and its impact on language acquisition. By targeting these grade levels, the study aimed to obtain comprehensive insights into the experiences and outcomes of learners actively engaged with digital tools. All teachers at the school were included in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought approval from the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent then after, she sought the approval of the School Principal of Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School to conduct the data gathering. When the permission was granted, the researcher asked permission from the respondents of the study (Grade 3-6 Learners and English Teachers for Grade 3-6) and explained the purpose of the data gathering. Information gathered from the respondents had undergone analysis and interpretation.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were analyzed using the following statistical tools to address the specific objectives of the study:

Frequency and Percentage count was used to summarize and identify and describe the demographic profiles of the teachers (age, sex, plantilla position, highest educational attainment, and grade level taught) and learners (age, sex, and grade level). This provided an overview of the respondents' characteristics.

Weighted Mean was utilized to analyze the teachers' and learners' perceptions of the utilization and effects digital platforms in English Language Teaching and Acquisition. This determined the average level of agreement or frequency based on the responses.

Chi-Square Test of Independence was employed to examine the significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and their perceptions of the utilization and effects of digital platforms. This test identified whether associations exist between categorical variables (e.g., sex, grade level taught) and perception scores.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The profile of the teacher respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher Respondents according to Age

Range	Frequency	Percentage
20-30 years old	1	10%
31-41 years old	3	30%
42-52 years old	3	30%
53-63 years old	3	30%
TOTAL	10	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents categorized according to age ranges. By grouping the respondents into specific age brackets, the analysis provides insight into the age diversity among the participants.

Based on the table, 30% of the teacher-respondents fall within the age ranges of 31-41, three (3) of them are 42-52 years old, and another three (3) of them are and 53-63. Only one (1) of the respondents is within the youngest age range of 20-30, indicating a relatively small representation of younger teachers. The uniform distribution across the three older age ranges suggests that most of the respondents are experienced teachers who may have been in the field for a significant period.

The distribution of age among the teacher-respondents implies a predominantly mature teaching workforce, likely with ample experience and expertise. This could be advantageous in maintaining established educational practices. The limited representation of younger teachers could affect the introduction of innovative and technologically advanced methods in teaching.

This result aligns with the findings of Ingersoll, et.al (2018) which highlighted that the teaching workforce globally tends to age over time due to the retention of experienced educators and challenges in recruiting younger ones. The study suggests that while experienced teachers contribute stability, the lack of younger educators may limit adaptability to educational reforms and the use of advanced technologies in teaching. Thus, the present findings reflect a common trend observed in educational systems worldwide.

b. Sex

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents according to Sex

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Female	8	80%
Male	2	20%
TOTAL	10	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents categorized by sex.

As shown in the table, there are 10 teacher-respondents in total, with a significant majority being female (80%), while only 20% are male. This indicates that the teaching profession, particularly in the context of this study, is predominantly female.

The higher percentage of female teacher-respondents suggests that the teaching profession may still be perceived as a more "feminine" career path, which could impact perspectives on teaching methodologies, classroom management, and learner engagement. This gender disparity might also reflect broader societal norms regarding gender roles in education.

The findings by Drudy (2008) emphasized the persistent feminization of the teaching profession globally, highlighting the need to address gender imbalances to create more inclusive educational environments. This pattern suggests that similar trends may be present in the setting of the current study, underscoring the importance of considering gender dynamics in educational research.

c. Plantilla Position

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents according to Plantilla Position

Plantilla Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher 1(Beginning)	1	10%
Teacher 2 (Beginning)	0	0%
Teacher 3 (Proficient)	8	80%
Master Teacher 1 (Highly Proficient)	1	10%
TOTAL	10	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents based on their plantilla position. This provides insight into the professional levels and qualifications of the respondents, which is vital in understanding their teaching experience and expertise.

As shown in the table, eight of the respondents or 80% hold the position of Teacher 3, categorized as proficient. Meanwhile, only one or 10% occupy the position of Teacher 1 categorized as beginning, none for Teacher 2 categorized as beginning, and one or 10% is a Master Teacher 1 categorized as highly proficient. This indicates that most respondents have attained a significant level of professional experience but are not yet at the most advanced rank.

The concentration of respondents in the Teacher 3 (Proficient) category suggests that the participants possess adequate classroom experience and expertise but may have limited items for promotion to the Master Teacher level.

Moreover, Ingersoll and Perda (2008) explored the barriers to career advancement in teaching. He emphasized that limited access to mentorship, professional development, and leadership opportunities can hinder teachers' growth and progression. These findings align with the distribution in the table, suggesting the need for more structured pathways for career growth and promotion among teachers.

d. Highest Educational Attainment

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents according to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree Holder	3	30%
Bachelor's Degree with Master's Units	3	30%
Master's Degree Holder	4	40%
TOTAL	10	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents according to their highest educational attainment. Understanding the academic qualifications of educators is essential, as these qualifications can influence teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

As shown in the table, 40% of the respondents hold a Master's degree, indicating a substantial commitment to advanced academic preparation. Additionally, 30% possess a Bachelor's degree with Master's units, suggesting they are actively pursuing further education. The remaining 30% are Bachelor's degree holders. This distribution demonstrates that a significant number of the respondents have engaged in or are engaging in postgraduate studies, reflecting a strong dedication to professional development.

The predominance of advanced degrees among the respondents implies a culture that values continuous learning and specialization within the teaching profession. Such qualifications may enhance instructional practices, contribute to better student performance, and open opportunities for career advancement. However, this trend also raises questions about equitable access to higher education, as factors like financial constraints, institutional support, and personal circumstances can influence a teacher's ability to pursue advanced degrees.

This analysis underscores the critical role of advanced educational attainment in the teaching profession and its potential impact on educational quality.

According to Schleicher (2016) teachers with higher educational qualifications often exhibit more effective teaching practices and greater confidence in their instructional strategies. The study highlights the importance of advanced education in enhancing teacher competencies, aligning with the patterns observed in the table.

e. Grade level taught

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents according to the Grade Level Taught

Grade Level Taught	Frequency	Percentage
Kinder (Key Stage 1)	2	20%
Grade 1-3 (Key Stage 1)	2	20%
Grade 4-6 (Key Stage 2)	6	60%
TOTAL	10	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents according to the grade levels taught. This data provides insight into the allocation of teaching resources across various educational stages, which can influence instructional strategies and learning outcomes.

According to the table, 60% of the respondents teach Grades 4 to 6 (Key Stage 2), indicating a majority focus on upper elementary education. In contrast, 20% of the respondents teach Kindergarten (Key Stage 1), and another 20% handle Grades 1 to 3 (also Key Stage 1). This distribution suggests a higher concentration of teachers in the intermediate grade levels compared to early childhood and primary levels.

These findings underscore the critical role of thoughtful teacher distribution across grade levels in enhancing educational outcomes.

Graham et al. (2003) examined the effects of teacher assignments on student performance. The research suggests that strategic teacher-to-classroom assignments can significantly impact student achievement, highlighting the importance of aligning teacher expertise with specific grade-level needs.

Similarly, this study recognizes that effective learning outcomes are not solely dependent on instructional materials or platforms, but also on how well these resources are matched with learners' needs and contexts. By drawing from this perspective, the present study underscores the importance of intentional and well-informed decisions in educational practices—whether in teacher assignments or in the integration of digital tools—to enhance overall learner performance.

2. What is the profile of the learner-respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Learner-Respondents according to Age

Range	Frequency	Percentage
8-9	36	33.96%
10-11	59	55.66%
12-13	11	10.38%
TOTAL	106	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of learner-respondents categorized according to age range.

According to the table, fifty-nine (59) of the learner-respondents belong to the age range of 10-11, accounting for 55.66% of the total respondents. This is followed by those aged 8-9, comprising 33.96%, while the smallest group belongs to the age range of 12-13, representing only 10.38%. The classification of learners into these age brackets aims to understand the composition of the respondents in relation to their developmental stages and educational levels.

The distribution suggests that most of the learners are within the middle childhood stage, which aligns with the typical age for students in Grades 3 to 6. The concentration of learners in the 10-11 age group may imply a balanced transition between primary and intermediate levels. The relatively lower representation of learners in the 12-13 age range may indicate that few older learners are present in these grade levels, potentially due to delayed entry or grade retention.

This result aligns with the findings of Hosain (2010) which highlighted that most learners in the intermediate grades typically fall within the 9-11 age range. The study found that deviations from the expected age range in primary education may be linked to grade retention or delayed school entry. The lower percentage of learners aged 12-13 in this present study may reflect similar trends, suggesting the need for interventions to support learners experiencing academic delays.

b. Sex

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Learner-Respondents according to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	51	48.1%
Female	55	51.9%
TOTAL	106	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of learner-respondents according to sex, providing insight into the gender composition of the present study. According to the data, 51 respondents are male, constituting 48.1% of the sample, while 55 respondents are female, accounting for 51.9%. This near-equal distribution suggests a balanced representation of genders among the learner-respondents.

This balanced gender representation among learner-respondents indicates an equitable participation rate in the educational context of the study. Such a group can foster diverse perspectives and interactions within the learning environment, potentially enriching the educational experience for all learners. This analysis underscores the importance of monitoring and promoting gender parity in education to ensure inclusive and equitable learning opportunities for all learners.

The data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2011) indicate that seven out of ten females aged six years old and over completed at least elementary education, a figure higher compared to that for males (65.1%). The data shows that a higher proportion of females aged six years old and over have completed at least elementary education compared to males is relevant to the present study as it reflects existing gender patterns in educational participation and achievement. This suggests that female learners may have slightly higher engagement or persistence in basic education, which can influence their exposure to and utilization of digital platforms in English language learning. In the context of this study, such a difference highlights the importance of considering learners' profiles, including gender, when examining the effectiveness and accessibility of digital tools. However, consistent with related studies, gender may not necessarily determine the effectiveness of digital platform use, but it provides useful background information in understanding learners' participation in the teaching-learning process.

c. Grade Level

Table 8
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Learner-Respondents according to Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 3	24	22.6%

Grade 4	25	23.6%
Grade 5	29	27.4%
Grade 6	28	26.4%
TOTAL	106	100%

The table presents the frequency and percentage distribution of learner-respondents across different grade levels, offering insight into the composition of the learner population. This distribution indicates an equitable representation across the specified grade levels, with a slightly higher proportion of respondents in Grades 5 and 6.

The near-equitable distribution of respondents suggests that the study captures a comprehensive perspective across these educational stages. This balance is crucial for ensuring that the findings are reflective of the experiences and opinions of learners at different stages of their elementary education.

Data from the Department of Education (DepEd) (2002) for School Year 2021–2022 indicates that enrollment figures across elementary grade levels are relatively consistent, with slight variations that could account for the distribution observed in the survey. Specifically, the DepEd reported that elementary enrollment reached 12.79 million in public schools during SY. '24-'25. This alignment between the survey data and national enrollment statistics underscores the importance of considering grade-level distributions when analyzing educational data.

3. What digital platforms are utilized by teachers in English Language Teaching?

Table 9
Digital Platforms used by Teacher-respondents in English Language Teaching

Digital Platform	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Google Classroom	1.4	Never
Kahoot	1	Never
Quizziz	1	Never
Duolingo	1.1	Never
Messenger	3.4	Always
Youtube	3.7	Always
Zoom	1.1	Never
Canva	1.6	Never
Total Weighted Mean	1.43	Never

Table 9 presents the digital platforms utilized by teacher-respondents in English language teaching, along with their corresponding weighted means and qualitative descriptions. The data reveal that commonly available communication and media platforms such as Messenger and YouTube are frequently used, both receiving “Always”.

In contrast, instructional and interactive learning tools like Google Classroom, Kahoot!, Quizizz, Duolingo, Zoom, and Canva are seldom used, all interpreted as “**Never**” based on their low weighted means. Overall, the total weighted mean of 1.43 indicates that digital platforms, particularly those designed for structured instruction and engagement, are generally underutilized by the respondents in the context of English language teaching.

The results show that Messenger and YouTube are consistently rated as “**Always**” used, while the other platforms are marked as “**Never.**” This implies that teachers tend to rely on digital tools that are widely accessible, familiar, and easy to integrate into their teaching practices. Messenger enables efficient communication through the delivery of instructions, learning materials, reminders, and feedback, allowing continuous interaction between teachers and learners. YouTube, on the other hand, offers a vast collection of audio-visual learning resources, including lessons on grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and comprehension, which help simplify complex English concepts and increase learner engagement.

In contrast, the non-use of other platforms may be attributed to limited digital infrastructure, lack of technical training, or insufficient institutional support, which restrict teachers from adopting more advanced or specialized educational technologies. As a result, teachers prefer platforms that are readily available and require minimal technical expertise, making Messenger and YouTube the most practical and effective tools for their instructional needs.

Similarly, a study by Noor et al. (2003) found that teachers tend to use digital platforms that are accessible, familiar, and easy to operate, such as social media and video-sharing tools, primarily for communication and resource sharing rather than structured instruction.

4. How do teacher-respondents perceive the utilization of digital platforms in English Language Teaching in terms of:
 - a. Usability and Integration

Table 10
Utilization of Digital Platforms in English Language Teaching in terms of Usability and Integration

Statement	Mean	Description
Digital platforms used in the classroom are easy to navigate and operate.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms are simple to incorporate into my daily English Lessons.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platform’s features encourage active participation among learners during English classes.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms in teaching helps me manage my time efficiently.	4.00	Strongly Agree

Digital platforms for teaching English are user friendly.	4.00	Strongly Agree
TOTAL	4.00	Strongly Agree

The table illustrates the perceived usability and integration of digital platforms in English language teaching, as assessed by the teacher-respondents. It presents the mean scores and qualitative descriptions for each statement.

All the statements have a mean score of **4.00**, which corresponds to **"Strongly Agree."** This indicates that the respondents find digital platforms highly user-friendly, simple to navigate, and efficient in managing time. They also perceive that these platforms actively support the learners engagement and participation during English classes, suggesting that digital tools can enhance interaction and collaboration in the classroom.

The findings indicate that digital platforms play a vital role in both classroom management and learner engagement in English classes, as reflected by the consistent **"Strongly Agree"** ratings of the teacher-respondents. Because digital platforms are easy to use and integrate into lessons, teachers are able to organize instructional materials, manage time efficiently, and maintain a smooth flow of classroom activities, leading to more effective classroom management. At the same time, tools such as Messenger and YouTube—frequently used in instruction—encourage active participation, provide instant communication and feedback, and present engaging multimedia content that captures learners' interest. These features motivate learners, support different learning styles, and promote interaction and collaboration, resulting in a more dynamic and responsive learning environment where learners are more involved and teachers can teach more efficiently.

These findings align with the study of Akram et al. (2002), which revealed that educators find digital platforms beneficial and accessible when integrated effectively. The consistently high ratings imply that the teacher-respondents are confident in using digital platforms as it offers various tools that can help create a proactive classroom environment and solutions to some limitations such as the pandemic.

b. Perceived Effectiveness

Table 11
Utilization of Digital Platforms in English Language Teaching in terms of Perceived Effect

Statement	Me an	Descripti on
Digital platforms enhance my ability to explain complex English Language Concepts.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms make teaching English more engaging for learners.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms provide a variety of teaching tools and resources for English Lessons.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree

Digital platforms enable me to adapt my teaching style more effectively to meet learners' needs.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms encourage active participation among learners during English classes.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms enhance learners' motivation to complete English tasks.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms help learners collaborate effectively in group activities.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms boost learners' confidence in completing English tasks.	4.0 0	Strongly Agree
TOTAL	4.0 0	Strongly Agree

The table presents the perceptions of teacher-respondents regarding the perceived effects of using digital platforms in teaching English. It shows the mean scores and qualitative descriptions for each statement, reflecting the teachers' assessment of how digital platforms influence their instructional practices and learners' engagement.

All statements received a consistent mean score of **4.00**, corresponding to **"Strongly Agree."** This indicates that the respondents unanimously perceive digital platforms as highly effective tools that enhance their ability to explain complex language concepts, provide varied teaching resources, and adapt their teaching styles to meet learners' needs. The data also suggest that digital platforms foster active participation, motivation, collaboration, and confidence among learners when completing English tasks.

The uniformity of responses signifies that the teacher-respondents strongly acknowledge the positive impact of digital platforms in enriching English language instruction. The perceived effectiveness of these platforms suggests that they are successfully integrated into the teaching strategies, promoting an engaging and interactive learning environment. Similarly, Alakrash et al. (2022), revealed that learners showed a high level of positive attitude towards using digital platforms, indicating their effectiveness in enhancing English language learning.

c. Overall Perception

Table 12
Utilization of Digital Platforms in English Language Teaching in Terms of Overall Perception

Statement	Mean	Description
Digital platforms promote creativity and critical thinking among learners.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms are a valuable enhancement to English language teaching.	4.00	Strongly Agree

Digital platforms make me feel confident about teaching English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms have provided a positive and beneficial experience for my teaching.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms are something I am willing to continue using in future English lessons.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms have improved my overall teaching effectiveness.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms improve my ability to provide instant feedback to learners.	4.00	Strongly Agree
TOTAL	4.00	Strongly Agree

The table presents the overall perceptions of teacher-respondents regarding the use of digital platforms in English language teaching. Each statement has a mean score of **4.00**, corresponding to "**Strongly Agree**," indicating a unanimous positive perception among the respondents.

The data suggest that teachers perceive digital platforms as effective tools for promoting creativity, critical thinking, and learner engagement. They also express confidence in using these platforms and recognize their value in enhancing teaching practices. Furthermore, there is a strong inclination to continue using digital platforms in future English lessons, reflecting the benefits they offer in the educational process.

These findings align with the study by Warschauer (2003) who highlighted that technology integration in language education enhances learning opportunities and supports diverse instructional strategies where users not only have access but are also confident in the use of technology for meaningful purposes. The respondents' positive perceptions—particularly in fostering creativity, critical thinking, and engagement—demonstrate that digital platforms are being utilized beyond basic functions and are contributing to improved teaching practices. Moreover, their willingness to continue using these tools aligns with Warschauer's assertion that when technology is perceived as beneficial and relevant, it becomes sustainably integrated into everyday practices, including education.

5. Is there a significant relationship between the teacher-respondents profile and their Perception on the Utilization of Digital Platforms on English Language Teaching?

Table 13
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between Teachers' profile and their perception on the utilization of Digital Platforms in terms of Usability and Integration in English Language Teaching

Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between Teachers' profile and their perception on the utilization of Digital Platforms in terms of Usability and Integration in English Language Teaching	P-value of Chi-square	Analysis	Remarks
Age	0.7991	P > 0.05	Not significant
Sex	1.0000	P > 0.05	Not significant
Plantilla Position	0.8546	P > 0.05	Not significant
Highest Educational Attainment	1.0000	P > 0.05	Not significant
Grade Level Taught	0.9979	P > 0.05	Not significant

Table 13 shows the Results of the Test of the significant relationship between the teachers' profile and their perception on the utilization of digital platforms in terms of usability and integration on English Language Teaching.

The results show that the Chi-square (χ^2) probability values are greater than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' profile and their perception on the utilization of digital platforms in terms of usability and integration on English Language Teaching. It implies that age, sex, plantilla position, highest educational attainment, and grade level taught of the teachers do not significantly affect their perception on the utilization of digital platforms in terms of usability and integration on English Language Teaching. It infers further that the teachers' profile and their perception on the usability and integration of digital platforms in teaching English Language are not significantly related.

The findings align with the study by Tondeur et al. (2017) indicating that demographic factors like age, gender, educational background, and teaching experience do not significantly influence teachers' perceptions and use of digital platforms. Instead, it emphasizes that teachers' beliefs about technology integration and their perceived ease of use have a more substantial impact. This further supports the result that the teachers' profile does not significantly affect their perception of digital platforms' usability and integration in English language teaching.

Table 14
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Teachers' Profile and their Perception on the Utilization of Digital Platforms on English Language Teaching in terms of Perceived Effect

Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Teachers' Profile and their Perception on the Utilization of Digital Platforms on English Language Teaching in terms of Perceived Effect	P-value of Chi-square	Analysis	Remarks
Age	0.7546	P > 0.05	Not significant
Sex	0.9856	P > 0.05	Not significant
Plantilla Position	0.9540	P > 0.05	Not significant
Highest Educational Attainment	1.0000	P > 0.05	Not significant
Grade Level Taught	0.9998	P > 0.05	Not significant

Table 14 shows the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' profile and their perception on the utilization of digital platforms on English Language Teaching in terms of perceived effect.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of Chi-square are greater than 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' perception on the utilization of digital platforms on English Language Teaching in terms of Perceived Effect. It states that the teachers' perception on the perceived on the utilization of the digital platforms on English Language Teaching in terms of Perceived Effect is not significantly affected by their age, sex, plantilla position, highest educational attainment, and grade level taught.

The results across all profile variables indicate that the perceived effect of digital platforms on English language teaching is uniform among teachers, regardless of their age, sex, plantilla position, educational attainment, or grade level taught, because these technologies are now widely institutionalized and embedded in everyday teaching practice.

Digital platforms such as messaging platforms, learning management systems, and video-sharing sites are commonly used by all teachers, providing the same access to instructional materials, communication channels, and interactive learning resources. This shared digital environment minimizes differences that might normally arise from demographic or professional backgrounds, allowing teachers to experience similar benefits in terms of usability, efficiency, and instructional support. Moreover, standardized school policies, training programs, and curriculum requirements ensure that teachers use these platforms in comparable ways, leading to consistent perceptions of their effectiveness. As a result, what shapes teachers' views is not who they are demographically, but how useful, easy, and relevant the digital tools are in supporting their teaching tasks, which explains why the perceived effect of digital platforms remains the same across all teacher groups.

The results are supported by the study of Diseko et al. (2022) titled "Factors Affecting Teacher Acceptance of Tablets in their Teaching Practice, emphasized that demographic variables such as age, gender, and teaching experience do not produce significant differences in teachers' perceptions of technology acceptance. Instead, the study stressed that factors such as perceived usefulness and other attitudinal variables play a more influential role in shaping teachers' acceptance of technology in instructional practices.

Table 15
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Profile and their Overall Perception on the Utilization of Digital Platforms on English Language Teaching

Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Profile and their overall Perception on the Utilization of Digital Platforms on English Language Teaching	P-value of Chi-square	Analysis	Remarks
Age	0.9894	P > 0.05	Not significant
Sex	0.8431	P > 0.05	Not significant
Plantilla Position	1.0000	P > 0.05	Not significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.9699	P > 0.05	Not significant
Grade Level Taught	1.0000	P > 0.05	Not significant

Table 15 displays the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' profile and their overall perception on the utilization of digital platforms on English Language Teaching.

The results reveal that probability values of χ^2 are greater than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' profile and their overall perception on the utilization of digital platforms on English Language Teaching.

It shows that the age, sex, plantilla position, highest educational attainment, and grade level taught of the teacher-respondents have no significant effect on the teachers' overall perception on utilizing digital platforms in teaching English Language.

A study by Widayanti and Suarnajaya (2021) aligns with these findings. The study found that teachers' demographic factors did not significantly influence their perceptions of digital platform effectiveness. The researchers emphasized that while technical skills and access to resources were challenges, demographic factors such as age or educational attainment had minimal impact on their perspectives.

6. How do the learner-respondent perceive the effects of digital platforms in English Language Acquisition in terms of:
 - a. Learner Engagement

Table 16
Perceived Effect of Digital Platforms in English Language Acquisition in terms of Learner Engagement

Statement	Mean	Description
Using Digital platforms motivate me to learn English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms makes me feel confident in participating in English activities.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms make collaborating with classmates during English lessons enjoyable.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Using Digital platforms help me feel more confident expressing myself in English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms encourages me to participate more actively in English activities.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Using Digital platforms keep my attention focused during English lessons.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms makes English activities more engaging than traditional methods.	3.25	Strongly Agree
Using Digital platforms helps me improve my English vocabulary and grammar.	3.75	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms allows me to read and comprehend English texts more effectively.	3.80	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms improve my listening and speaking skills in English.	4.00	Strongly Agree

Table 16 displays the results indicate that learner-respondents have a positive perception on the effects of digital platforms on learner engagement in English Language Acquisition. All indicators received mean scores, ranging from **3.25 to 4.00**, with descriptions interpreted as **Strongly Agree**, suggesting a consistently favorable response across all engagement-related aspects.

The highest mean scores (**M = 4.00**) are recorded for statements related to motivation to learn English, confidence in participating and expressing oneself, enjoyment of collaboration with classmates, active participation, attention during lessons, and improvement in listening and speaking skills. These findings imply that digital platforms significantly enhance learners' motivation, confidence, and active involvement in English learning activities, while also supporting the development of productive language skills.

Meanwhile, slightly lower yet still high mean scores are observed for statements regarding the effectiveness of digital platforms in making English activities more engaging than traditional methods (**M = 3.25**), improving vocabulary and grammar (**M = 3.75**), and enhancing reading comprehension (**M = 3.80**). Although these aspects received comparatively lower means, the results still reflect strong agreement, indicating that learners perceive digital platforms as beneficial instructional tools across various language skills.

Overall, the data suggest that digital platforms play a significant role in fostering learner engagement by promoting motivation, confidence, collaboration, and skill development in English. The consistently high ratings highlight the effectiveness of digital platforms as engaging and supportive tools in English language instruction.

This aligns with Schindler et al. (2017) findings emphasizing that the use of digital technologies in language and higher education contexts significantly enhances learner engagement by promoting interaction, collaboration, and active learning, which in turn improves learners' motivation and participation.

b. Impact

Table 17
Perceived Effect of Digital Platforms in English Language Acquisition in terms of Impact

Statement	Mean	Description
Digital platforms encourage creativity in writing and other English-related tasks.	3.74	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms boost my confidence in completing English writing assignments.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms helps me improve my pronunciation in English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms helps me understand English lessons better.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Using Digital platforms improves my ability to use English in speaking and writing.	4.00	Strongly Agree
The use of Digital platforms makes English lessons more enjoyable and interesting.	4.00	Strongly Agree

The data presented in Table 17 indicates that learner-respondents perceive digital platforms as having a highly positive impact on English Language learning. All indicators obtained **high mean scores**, ranging from **3.74 to 4.00**, with all descriptions interpreted as **Strongly Agree**, reflecting a strong consensus among respondents regarding the effectiveness of digital platforms.

The highest mean scores (**M = 4.00**) were recorded for statements indicating that digital platforms boost learners' confidence in completing English tasks, promote creativity and critical thinking, and serve as a valuable enhancement to English language learning. Additionally, respondents strongly agreed that digital platforms contribute to a positive and beneficial learning experience and increase confidence in speaking and writing English. These results suggest that digital platforms not only support learners' academic performance but also enhance teachers' instructional confidence and effectiveness.

Meanwhile, a slightly lower yet still high mean score was obtained for the statement related to enhancing learners' motivation to complete English tasks (**M = 3.74**). Although this indicator received the lowest mean among the items, it still reflects strong agreement, indicating that digital platforms remain effective in motivating learners and encouraging collaboration in group activities.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that digital platforms have a substantial positive impact on learning processes in English Language Acquisition, particularly in fostering learner confidence, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking.

The results affirm that digital platforms play a significant and transformative role in English Language learning. The consistently high mean scores indicate that digital platforms enhance learner motivation, collaboration, confidence, and higher-order thinking skills, while also providing teachers with a more positive and effective teaching experience. These outcomes highlight the dual impact of digital platforms in strengthening both learner engagement and instructional practices.

This aligns with Handayani's (2024) finding that the integration of digital tools significantly enhances learner engagement, motivation, and collaborative learning by providing immersive and interactive experiences that support language acquisition and learner autonomy.

c. Overall Perceived Effect

Table 18
Perceived Effect of Digital Platforms in English Language Acquisition in terms of Overall Perceived Effect

Statement	Mean	Description
Digital platforms allow me to practice English skills more effectively.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms help clarify difficult English concepts through interactive content.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms improve my ability to use English in real-life scenarios.	3.25	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms enhance my understanding of English grammar.	3.80	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms are helpful tool for learning English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms excite me about future English lessons.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms make me feel more interested in learning English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms have been a positive experience for me.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms have improved my overall ability to use English.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms should be used more often for English learning.	4.00	Strongly Agree

Table 18 presents the Perceived effect of Digital Platforms in English Language Acquisition in terms of Overall Perceived Effect.

The results presented indicate that learner-respondents overwhelmingly perceive digital platforms as highly beneficial to their English language learning. All statements have mean scores ranging from **3.25 to 4.00**, and all are interpreted as “**Strongly Agree**,” showing a strong consensus about the positive effects of digital technology in English learning environments.

Notably, the highest mean values (**M = 4.00**) are consistently recorded across multiple dimensions such as practicing English skills more effectively, clarifying difficult English concepts through interactive content, being helpful tools for learning English, excitement about future English lessons, increased interest in learning English, positive personal learning experience, improved overall English ability, and the belief that digital platforms should be used more often.

These results suggest that learners perceive digital platforms not only as effective for skill practice and comprehension but also as motivational tools that increase interest, engagement, and positive attitudes toward future English learning.

Meanwhile, slightly lower but still strong agreement is observed for the statements “Digital platforms improve my ability to use English in real-life scenarios” (**M = 3.25**) and “Digital platforms enhance my understanding of English grammar” (**M = 3.80**). Though somewhat lower than other items, these scores still reflect a high level of affirmation that digital platforms contribute meaningfully to practical and structural aspects of language learning.

This aligns with the findings of Yolanda et al. (2005) indicating that learners perceive digital platforms as an effective and flexible tool that enhances their language acquisition. Platforms such as YouTube, Duolingo, Zoom, Google Classroom, and WhatsApp were particularly valued for their ability to provide authentic English exposure, interactive learning experiences, and opportunities for autonomous learning.

7. Is there a significant relationship between the learner-respondents’ profile and their perception on the effect of digital platforms on English Language?

Table 19
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Learners’ Profile and their Perception on the Effect of Digital Platforms on English Language Acquisition

Learner’s Profile and their Perception on the Perceived Effect of Digital Platforms on English Language Acquisition	P-value of Chi-square	Analysis
Age	0.99491	P > 0.05
Sex	0.99993	P > 0.05
Grade Level	0.99999	P > 0.05

The result of the test of significant relationship between the learners' profile and their perception on the effect of digital platforms on English Language acquisition are displayed in Table 19.

It is reflected from the table that the Chi-square probability values are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the learners' profile and their perception on the effect of digital platforms on English Language Acquisition.

It shows that the learners' perceived effect of digital platforms on English Language is not significantly affected by their age, sex, and grade level. It states further that the learners' perception on the effect of digital platforms on English Language Acquisition and their profile are not significantly related.

A study by Berková et al. (2024) examines how socio-demographic factors, such as gender, field of study, and form of study, influence the utilization of digital learning platforms among university students. The research found that while gender did not significantly affect the use of digital platforms, the field of study and form of study (e.g., full-time vs. part-time) did have a notable impact on students' engagement with these platforms. This suggests that certain demographic factors may influence learners' perceptions and usage of digital learning tools.

These findings provide relevant support to the present study, as they highlight how certain socio-demographic factors can influence the utilization of digital learning platforms. While their study indicates that gender does not significantly affect platform use, it emphasizes that variables such as field of study and form of study play a crucial role in shaping students' engagement. In relation to the present study, which examines the use of digital platforms in English Language Teaching (ELT), this suggests that learners' interaction insights reinforce the need to consider learner differences when evaluating the effectiveness of digital platforms, as variations in engagement and perception may impact language acquisition outcomes.

8. What are the challenges encountered by the teachers and learners in the utilization of digital platforms?

Table 20
Challenges Encountered by Teachers on the Utilization of Digital Platforms for English Language Teaching

STATEMENT	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTION
Digital platforms cannot be used effectively due to poor internet connectivity.	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms cannot be used effectively due to my lack of adequate training.	3.25	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms are hindered by insufficient access to digital tools or resources (e.g., computers, tablets).	3.15	Agree

Digital platforms make attention and engagement more challenging.	1.05	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms do not align well with the English curriculum and teaching objectives.	1.15	Strongly Disagree
Preparing lessons and materials using Digital platforms is time-consuming.	1.10	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms fail to accurately measure students' English language skills.	1.30	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms are a struggle to adapt traditional teaching methods.	1.12	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms cause learners difficulty in navigating or understanding how to use them.	1.19	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms present increased challenges due to limited administrative support for their implementation.	3.12	Agree
Digital platforms are affected by the lack of access to devices or reliable internet, which impacts participation.	3.25	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms face resistance from learners in terms of learning through them.	1.50	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms disrupt lessons due to frequent technical issues (e.g., software glitches, platform crashes).	4.00	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms do not effectively accommodate diverse learning styles.	1.25	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms present a barrier due to the cost of subscriptions or licenses.	3.60	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms lack interactive features suitable for teaching English.	1.15	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms make teaching English challenging due to limited content customization options.	1.10	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms affect learning due to learner distractions from non-educational features.	3.74	Strongly Agree
Digital platforms make it more difficult to monitor learners' individual progress.	1.17	Strongly Disagree

Table 20 presents the challenges encountered by teachers in the utilization of digital platforms for English language teaching, highlighting the barriers that educators perceive as most significant.

Among the items rated with **Agree** are teachers identified **limited access to digital tools and resources** (M = 3.15) and **insufficient administrative support for the integration of digital platforms** (M = 3.12) as notable challenges. These findings indicate that while teachers recognize the potential of digital platforms, institutional and

resource-related constraints limit their effective utilization. The lack of consistent access to technology and limited support from school administrators may reduce teachers' capacity to fully implement digital tools in English language instruction.

The items that received a **Strongly Agree** rating reflect the most critical challenges faced by teachers. **Poor internet connectivity** (M = 4.00) emerged as the most significant barrier, underscoring the fundamental role of reliable technological infrastructure in digital teaching. Additionally, **inadequate training on the use of digital platforms** (M = 3.25) was strongly acknowledged, suggesting that teachers require more professional development opportunities to effectively integrate digital tools into their teaching practices. Other major challenges include **limited access to appropriate digital devices** (M = 3.45) and **difficulty in motivating learners when using digital platforms** (M = 3.75), which point to both logistical and pedagogical concerns.

These findings are supported by the study of Sim et al. (2023) where it similarly identified **inadequate training, unstable internet connectivity, and limited access to digital devices** as major obstacles to effective digital integration in English language teaching. The alignment of the present findings with existing literature reinforces the conclusion that addressing infrastructural limitations and enhancing teacher training are essential for the successful and sustainable use of digital platforms in English language education.

Table 21
Challenges Encountered by Learners on the Utilization of Digital Platforms for English Language Acquisition

STATEMENT	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTION
Poor internet connectivity disrupts my access to digital platforms for learning.	3.86	Strongly Agree
I do not have enough devices (e.g., smartphones, computers, tablets) to use digital platforms.	3.12	Agree
Navigating or using digital platforms is difficult for me.	1.77	Disagree
Instructions or activities on digital platforms are not always clear to understand.	1.08	Strongly Disagree
I feel less engaged and motivated when using digital platforms for English lessons.	2.04	Disagree
Distractions from non-educational features (e.g., ads, notifications) affect my focus.	3.31	Strongly Agree
I find it hard to participate in online lessons due to a lack of reliable internet access.	3.81	Strongly Agree
My learning style is not well-supported by digital platforms.	1.18	Strongly Disagree
Some digital platforms are not interactive enough for learning English.	1.37	Strongly Disagree
The use of digital platforms is not always relevant to what I need to learn in English.	1.72	Strongly Disagree
I feel frustrated when technical issues (e.g., glitches, platform errors) interrupt my lessons.	1.73	Disagree
I do not receive enough support or guidance when I struggle with digital platforms.	1.86	Disagree

Communicating with teachers or classmates is more challenging on digital platforms.	1.27	Strongly Disagree
I feel less connected to my teacher and classmates during online lessons.	1.24	Strongly Disagree
I often experience delays or confusion during online classes using digital platforms.	1.12	Strongly Disagree
I prefer traditional classroom activities over using digital platforms.	1.22	Strongly Disagree
The cost of internet data or device maintenance is a barrier to my participation.	3.32	Strongly Disagree
I find it difficult to track my progress on digital platforms.	1.81	Disagree
I find it difficult to track my progress on digital platforms.	1.26	Disagree
My parents or guardians are not familiar enough with digital platforms to help me.	3.15	Agree
The pace of lessons on digital platforms is too fast or too slow for me.	1.25	Strongly Disagree
I find it difficult to collaborate with my classmates during online activities.	1.19	Strongly Disagree
Digital platforms do not provide enough opportunities for speaking or practicing oral English.	1.12	Strongly Disagree
Reading materials or text on digital platforms are hard to follow or understand.	1.26	Strongly Disagree
I feel overwhelmed by the number of activities or tasks assigned on digital platforms.	1.90	Disagree
Some features of digital platforms are distracting and make learning harder.	1.50	Disagree
I experience anxiety when using digital platforms due to lack of confidence or skills.	3.12	Agree
My learning progress is negatively affected when technical support is unavailable.	3.10	Agree
I feel unmotivated to participate when digital platforms have repetitive or unengaging content.	1.26	Strongly Disagree
My learning is negatively affected when I must share devices with family members.	3.18	Agree

Table 21 presents the challenges encountered by learners in the utilization of digital platforms for English language acquisition. The table categorizes these challenges according to weighted mean scores and corresponding descriptions, ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. Analyzing these results sheds light on the barriers that learners face when using digital tools for language learning.

To begin with, examining the items marked as **Strongly Disagree**, most learners do not believe that digital platforms fail to support their learning styles ($M = 1.18$), are not interactive enough ($M = 1.37$), or lack relevance to their English learning needs ($M = 1.72$). Similarly, there is strong disagreement that digital platforms hinder their communication with teachers and classmates ($M = 1.27$), cause confusion or delays ($M = 1.12$), or are less preferred compared to traditional classroom settings ($M = 1.22$). This suggests that students generally perceive digital platforms as aligned with their educational needs.

For items that received a **Disagree** rating, learners generally disagree with the idea that navigating digital platforms is difficult (M = 1.77) or that they feel less motivated and engaged during digital English lessons (M = 2.04). There is also a disagreement that technical issues frequently interrupt their learning (M = 1.73) and that tracking progress on digital platforms is challenging (M = 1.26). These perceptions indicate that most students have adapted to the use of digital tools.

When considering the items marked as **Agree**, significant challenges emerge. Learners agree that a lack of sufficient devices (M = 3.12), the absence of technical support (M = 3.10), and the need to share devices with family members (M = 3.18) negatively impact their learning experience. Additionally, anxiety due to insufficient digital skills (M = 3.12) further complicates their ability to use these platforms effectively.

Finally, the items that received a **Strongly Agree** rating highlight the most critical barriers. Poor internet connectivity (M = 3.86), distractions from non-educational features (M = 3.31), and unreliable internet access (M = 3.81) are the most significant hurdles. The high cost of internet data and device maintenance (M = 3.32) is also seen as a considerable obstacle, suggesting socioeconomic factors play a role in digital learning accessibility.

A study by Gusman et al. (2023) corroborates these findings. The study highlights that students often encounter challenges such as limited access to digital technology, inadequate digital literacy, and technical issues like poor internet connectivity, which hinder their learning experience. Additionally, the study emphasizes the importance of addressing these challenges to enhance the effectiveness of digital platforms in English language acquisition.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study revealed that the utilization of digital platforms in English Language Teaching (ELT) at Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School plays a significant and positive role in enhancing learners' English language acquisition. The findings indicate that digital platforms effectively promote learner engagement, motivation, confidence, and active participation, while also supporting the development of essential language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Moreover, these platforms contribute to improved comprehension, creativity, and overall proficiency in English. Despite minor challenges and variations in certain aspects of use, the overall results demonstrate that digital tools serve as valuable and effective instructional resources. Therefore, the integration of digital platforms in ELT is highly beneficial and should be continuously strengthened, with attention given to addressing existing gaps and challenges to further improve teaching practices and optimize learners' language development.

Recommendations

The researcher offers the following recommendations:

For Educational Policymakers, to strengthen support for the integration of digital platforms in English Language Teaching by developing clear policies, allocating sufficient funding, and ensuring equitable access to digital tools and internet connectivity. They should also promote continuous professional development programs that equip teachers with the necessary digital competencies.

For School administrators, to actively support the implementation of digital platforms by providing adequate infrastructure, technical assistance, and monitoring mechanisms. They are also encouraged to foster a school environment that promotes innovation, collaboration, and effective use of technology in teaching and learning.

For Project Development Officers, to design and implement programs that enhance the use of digital platforms in ELT, focusing on addressing identified gaps such as limited resources or training needs. They should also evaluate the effectiveness of these programs and ensure their sustainability through continuous improvement.

For Learning Resource Management System (LRMS) Coordinators to curate, develop, and organize high-quality, accessible, and curriculum-aligned digital learning materials. They should also provide guidance and support to teachers in selecting and utilizing appropriate digital resources to enhance English language instruction.

For Teachers, to continuously integrate digital platforms into their teaching practices to promote learner engagement and improve language acquisition. They should also pursue ongoing training to enhance their digital literacy and adopt innovative strategies that cater to diverse learners' needs.

For Parents, to actively support their children's use of digital platforms at home by providing guidance, monitoring usage, and encouraging productive and responsible engagement with digital learning tools.

For Learners, to actively participate in digital learning activities, utilize available platforms responsibly, and take initiative in improving their English language skills through consistent practice and engagement.

For the researcher, to further explore the use of digital platforms in different contexts and expand the scope of the study to include additional variables that may influence English language acquisition.

For Future researchers, to conduct similar studies using larger samples, varied research designs, or different educational settings to validate and enrich the findings. They may also investigate other factors such as technological readiness, learning styles, and long-term impacts of digital platform integration in ELT.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with established ethical standards in educational research. Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher secured

permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and the School Principal of Cabannungan 2nd Elementary School. The purpose, scope, and procedures of the study were clearly explained to all respondents before data gathering commenced. Since the learner-respondents were elementary pupils, proper consent and permission were observed through the approval of school authorities, and participation was treated with utmost care and responsibility.

The respondents were informed that their participation was voluntary and that they had the right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequence. The researcher ensured that no respondent was forced, pressured, or influenced to participate. All information gathered from the teacher- and learner-respondents was used solely for academic and research purposes.

Confidentiality and privacy were strictly maintained throughout the conduct of the study. The names, identities, and personal information of the respondents were not disclosed in any part of the research. Data were presented in summarized and statistical form to protect the anonymity of the participants. Furthermore, the researcher ensured that the study did not cause harm, discomfort, or disadvantage to the respondents.

The researcher also observed honesty, objectivity, and integrity in the collection, analysis, interpretation, and presentation of data. All sources used in the study were properly acknowledged to avoid plagiarism. Thus, the study complied with ethical standards by upholding voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, privacy, objectivity, and respect for all participants.

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